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Knowledge of Primary Health Care Workers Towards Medical Waste Management in Model Health Care Facilities in Rivers South East Senatorial District

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Abstract

This study focused on the knowledge of primary health care workers towards medical waste management (MWM) in model health facilities in Rivers South-East Senatorial District. Two objectives, two research questions, and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study with the sample size of 600 through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument for eliciting data was titled Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Medical Waste Management (KAPMUM) with the reliability coefficient of 0.70 which was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. Data collected were analysed using SPSS version 23.0. The results showed that 501(89.5%) of the respondents had good knowledge of MWM while 59(10.5%) had poor knowledge. The result also showed that there was a significant difference between gender and knowledge of PHC workers towards medical waste management in model health facilities in Rivers South East Senatorial District (X^2 -value= 34.356; df =1; $p<0.05$). Level of education was significant (X^2 -value= 326.247; df =3; $p<0.05$). Work experience showed significant (X^2 -value= 84.069; df =3; $p<0.05$) with medical waste management. It was concluded that there is need to maintain knowledge of healthcare workers towards medical waste management in model health facilities. Based on the findings, it was recommended that education and training are the best methods to manage the adverse health effects that are common in medical waste management.

Keywords: knowledge, demographic characteristics, medical waste management, primary health care workers.